

IMPACT OF MARKETPLACES ON THE BEHAVIOUR OF UZBEK CONSUMERS AND THEIR WILLINGNESS TO CHANGE FROM TRADITIONAL TO DIGITAL PURCHASING PERCEPTION IN 2024

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Abstract. *In this article we are eager to discuss the change in consumer behaviour in Uzbek markets, particularly the acceptance of online marketplaces despite the habit and preferences to traditional shopping and what caused people to change their perception. Globalism and conservatism usually do not go together and colliding in one place may have unpredictable results in consumer behaviour. Moreover, there is going to be a study on external and internal reasons for shaped shopping habits of Uzbek people. From the internal point of view, we are going to look into consumer's psychological behaviour and understand how locals shaped their opinion. The conceptual framework was designed to overlook new and old generations so we could have a better understanding. For the external part we are going to focus on the businesses, specifically the current state of online marketplaces in Uzbekistan and their contribution to the development of online business. With the advancement of e-commerce technology, online platforms have emerged that provide an alternative to traditional methods of buying and selling. With the continuous growth of the Internet user base and the increasing technological literacy of the population, the prospects for e-commerce in Uzbekistan remain encouraging.*

Keywords: *marketplace, consumers, purchasing power, conservatism, confirmation bias, Uzbekistan, bazaar, traditions, online market, seller, buyer, virtual space, online business, globalisation.*

Introduction

1.1 Context of the thesis

Most of the businesses are gradually shifting from selling their services and products into the online market, which leads to digital adoption of the consumers as well. In fact new trends drive better service in online marketplaces and no less than 60% of worldwide businesses are already introduced to the online environment (Nagar, 2022). Humankind has always been evolving and one of the factors that could identify a country's development or economic prosperity is by what was imported and exported to the city centre (Jacobs, 1969; Stobart & Van Damme, 2016).

As an example, The Silk Road remained one of the important cross-culture interactions between China and the West through Eurasia, Victor H. Mair (2018) states that "even before the opening of the Silk Roads by Zhang Qian in the late 2nd century BC, there was an informal system of contact and exchange across the expanse of Eurasia". Traders of different goods like silk, spices, tea, ivory, cotton were finding either way to sell products even when the marketplace was not officially known and 'opened' to usage. Cities through which The Silk Road went through were blooming and were thought to be the most civilised (Liu, 2010).

Economic stability makes people sure about their future and the consumer's demand creates market opportunity for the suppliers. Nowadays, subsequently in-store owners are seeking new ventures and with access to the internet the growth of marketplaces are seen as a necessity. Online marketplaces deserve the recognition it gets since it ensures new job opportunities in numerous sectors thus influencing overall development of the nation.

With the Covid-19 “non-key firms had a harder time dealing with the economic downturn of the pandemic” Stemmler (2023) explains in his working papers at the International Labour Organization. Declining sales and low revenue at these so-called non-essential businesses pushed them to enter low barrier marketplaces and adjust their services for the sake of surviving the game.

After experiencing instability suppliers are less likely to stick with the option of traditional offline stores, which is why e-commerce allows businesses to extend to a wider consumer range, as well as its ability to allow customers to shop at their convenience (Taher, 2021). Looking at the prospects of digital shopping after the pandemic period it has been calculated that e-commerce faces 300 to 350 million shoppers by the year 2025 (D’Aprizio, 2021). Customers and suppliers reached synergy (Sezer, Melik, 2022) and the marketplace can be seen as a wholesome organism that works for the benefit of both sides.

Recent studies have shown that marketplaces can provide platforms for alternative consumption models of sharing and upcycling, reuse and recycling (Sezer, Melik, 2022). E-commerce inclusivity makes the platform flexible and ‘customer’ can become a ‘seller’, meaning that anyone can be in the business. Low entry requirement guarantees a safe space where “diverse people feel they have an equal right to be” (Morales, 2011). Dutch based company OLX Group - “global online marketplace, buying and selling services and goods such as electronics, fashion items, furniture” (Crunchbase, 2023) is a perfect example of e-commerce which opens their spots in each country and localises their businesses allowing everyone to register and sell their products.

Problem statement

Since we have established what is a marketplace, what role it plays in the economic and social sphere and what future it withholds, we may proceed into analysing how people in Uzbekistan are reacting to changes of global market and integration of technologies into their daily purchasing experience.

Adapting to changes isn't the strongest trait of the people of Central Asia and as Matveeva (1999) states in her article ‘Democratisation, Legitimacy and Political Change in Central Asia’ that the political culture of post-Soviet countries, specifically those who are located in Central Asia are highly conservative. Our community may cherish and enjoy the traditional ways of shopping in public places like markets and open-roof bazaars with the immediate access to the product, but somehow globalisation has its own way of building new perceptions. Interestingly, not only it changed the perspective of the buyer, but it also changed the way people started to sell and promote their product.

In 2024 Uzbekistan has been experiencing dynamic growth in its economy over the past couple of years, including in the field of e-commerce. Marketplaces that bring together sellers and buyers in virtual space are becoming increasingly popular in the country. In this article, we will look at the current state of marketplaces in Uzbekistan and their contribution to the development of online business

We may think that globalisation may have a key role in developing people’s habits, however there is more to that. In a pandemic year, the closure of stores, non-food markets,

supermarkets, manufacturers needed to pay attention to online sales and look for potential buyers. Online purchases and home delivery was a necessity back then, however in 2024 when everything came back to 'normal' as it was and there is no need for staying at home, what is the necessity of virtual online shopping? Has the shopping perception of Uzbek netizens finally changed and why did it take only 3 years?

Hypothesis

In this dissertation, we are going to look through all of the existing markets available in Tashkent, Uzbekistan. Focusing on the offline store with online stores as well.

Our hypothesis claims that shift in consumer behaviour may be a reason of outdated methods of shopping and Uzbek people were ready to change from traditional shopping experience to digital purchases

Results of the Study

Starting with the history of Uzbekistan, the country declared their independence in 1991 and the newly independent state is almost 33 years old. Compared to developed countries, Central Asian states are at the start of the development and it would be crucial to highlight how long it took to shape west European states. It is obvious that Uzbekistan started to develop democratisation - new political and educational changes, in the meantime society and new ideologies started to invade and build new communities too. However, Matveeva claims that: "even compared to other CIS states, the culture of Central Asia is highly conservative" (1999). Which means that even though we started to have new things, Uzbek people haven't forgotten about their traditions, family, tribal and ethnic loyalties.

Just to give an example how slow our society comes into accepting something new and adapting into 'western' standards, looking back in 2017 most of the international franchises in Uzbekistan were not existing compared to nowadays in 2024. For instance, if we take the food industry, in 2017 there was news announcing that in the next upcoming year fast food chain "KFC" will enter the Uzbek market. You might think that a brand like 'McDonald's' would certainly be in the market, however there is no sight of the brand entering Uzbekistan in the near 2024 year.

Same goes for international clothes brands. In 2018 Uzbek people were gradually introduced to mass market brands like "Mango", "Benetton" and "Lc Waikiki" and it has been announced recently that in 2024 worldwide known brand "Zara" is entering Uzbek market. It is important to mention that before 2018 Uzbeks were only able to buy these brand clothes from buyers on Instagram pages. Usually, they had someone in Turkey or Germany that ships these brands to our country, in fact, it was hard to find a decent buyer, who delivered on time and was not overpricing cargo.

In 2018 it was expected and natural to search up a brand you like and put clothes into the 'basket', however as an inexperienced society in Uzbekistan people tend to avoid things that are unfamiliar and mostly are scared that their clothes may not come eventually. Personally, one of the authors of this article tried to do online shopping in 2021 through Alibaba and Aliexpress popular Chinese websites, and most of the purchased items did not arrive till this day. Not only Uzbek netizens have conservative opinions about shopping online but trust issues as well.

Traditional 'Open-air' Bazaars and Stores

When it comes to traditional bazaars, in Uzbek culture, people come to open-air bazaars for the unlimited access to fresh vegetables, fruits, meat, dairy products and imported cheese, sausages from different countries and it is only food sections. Traditional bazaars play a massive

role in trade, just to name a few, we have food bazaars located in every district of Tashkent. Fast and easy access, does not require a lot of footsteps to shop and buy groceries.

Moreover, Uzbekistan has a 24/7 food and beverage retail chain store called “Korzinka” that supplies with everything that is essential for the household. Most of the people prefer to shop in the bazaars for the cheaper option, since you may bargain with the seller, but in-store places like “Korzinka” all of the prices are fixed, so some people may prefer to shop there.

Goods and clothes Bazaars may be even in more demand for middle class citizens, since all of the products are considered having lower price than the market and fairly cheaper than mass-market clothes brands imported to Uzbekistan. In Clothes Bazaars you have hundreds of sellers in one place selling regular clothes from China or Turkey or you may even encounter brand knock-offs.

Some common types of marketplaces in Uzbekistan include Bazaars/Markets: Traditional open-air markets where you can find a wide range of goods, including fresh produce, spices, clothing, and handmade crafts. Abu Saxiy Bazaar in Tashkent and Chorsu Bazaar are examples.

Shopping Centres/Malls

In urban areas, you'll find modern shopping centres and malls that house a mix of local and international brands. These are often air-conditioned and provide a more modern shopping experience. Most of the well-known and operating malls are Samarkand Darvoza, Rivera, Next however in those places, you have limited options of purchasing goods.

Recently, on the 29th of February there was a grand opening of Tashkent city mall, located in the city centre. This mall is considered as a high-class shopping hub and the price segmentation is quite high.

Specialised Markets

Some markets specialise in specific goods, such as textiles, electronics, or handmade crafts. These markets cater to individuals looking for particular products. Most of these items is hard to find in malls or in the city centre. Usually, if you need electronic equipment like phones, laptops or kitchen appliances, there is a place called ‘Malika’.

International e-markets in Uzbekistan

In the late 90s with the advancement of e-commerce technology, online platforms have emerged that provide an alternative to traditional methods of buying and selling. Let us take as an example international brands like Amazon, eBay, Alibaba, all of those platforms serve the purpose of selling goods online for the convenience of the customers. Naturally, these brands do international shipping, however for Central Asia, specifically Uzbekistan delivery takes more than 2 weeks if not more. Most of the delivery ships through international service “DHL” with high service fee, compared to European or American prices

In 2004, the Russian company launched the largest online retailer - “Wildberries”, which positioned itself as a fashionable online store of clothes, shoes and accessories. Nowadays in the app you can find electronics and goods for your house as well, so the variety of items does not limit in this internet market. News Portal “UzDaily” reported in February 2022 that Wildberries is planning to enter the Uzbek market. They stated that: “Residents of the country will have access to a wide range of goods, and entrepreneurs will be able to develop their business by expanding sales channels and opening joint partner outlets.” Nowadays there are 57 pick-up points.

Uzdaily.uz (2023), states that by 2025 Wildberries in Uzbekistan will be the second country that has the biggest logistical centre outside of Russia and it is expected to have more than 7

thousand workplaces for Uzbek citizens. Hence, entrepreneurs will have less logistics costs which will affect the prices on goods and their willingness to buy increases.

On the other hand, we have one more competitor “Ozon” - which is also a Russian marketplace that opened in 2022. The company stated that in 2024 it intends to develop its own logistics infrastructure in the country, including warehouse complexes and delivery services, as well as a franchise network of branded pick-up points. However, users in “Ozon” platform have complaint that some of the items in the marketplace are not shipping to Uzbekistan and they take extra payment for the delivery, meanwhile in “Wildberries” shipment is free and all of the products are could be delivered to Uzbekistan.

Uzum / Sello.uz e-market

Till 2022 citizens had two options whether to go to Bazaar or retail stores to get goods. In 2022 a new online marketplace “Uzum ” introduced itself in the Uzbek market. The concept of ‘Uzum’ market is to sell products online whether it is clothes, food options or goods for home. Local newspaper, *Repost.uz*, (2023) reported that in just a few months after operating, the Uzum Market marketplace launched about 60 pick-up points, and by the end of March the company will launch its 100th pick-up point. Goods of more than 200 thousand unique products with fast delivery have become available to residents of all regions of the country.

With the development of marketplaces in Uzbekistan, there is a transition from traditional trading methods to modern online platforms. This provides convenience to buyers and sellers and also helps to expand the market for various goods and services.

Newly opened online marketplaces like ‘Uzum’, ‘Wildberries’, ‘Ozon’ have their own way of dealing in the Uzbek market. Nowadays this segment is developing rapidly, and home shopping is in demand among consumers, which only took 3 years to change netizens opinion

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Challenges and Prospects

Despite the positive aspects, there are challenges such as transaction security, competition, and conservative consumers. However, with the continuous growth of the Internet user base and the increasing technological literacy of the population, the prospects for e-commerce in Uzbekistan remain encouraging. Marketplaces play a key role in the development of e-commerce in Uzbekistan, providing convenient and efficient ways to buy and sell goods.

Uzbek market continuous to expand and with economic growth in Uzbekistan, country has created prospects for the future digital purchases. Diversifying the economy with export opportunities, reducing the dependence on the local businesses and focusing on the international trade.

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